

Evaluation of Subsurface Damage on Structural Scale with Integrated Full Field Approaches

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Engineering and
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CERTIFICATION
FOR DESIGN:
RESHAPING THE
TESTING PYRAMID

30/05/2023

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Introduction

- Composite materials are uniquely susceptible to damage
- Various detection methods exist
- Many were developed, and suitable for planar specimens
- Real composite components are rarely planar
- There are relatively few methods for complex geometry
- Very few methods can detect wrinkling, a common manufacturing flaw

Thermo-elastic Stress Analysis

- Relates temperature measurements to stress state
- Classically considered surface technique
 - Surface stress state is useful in itself
 - Stress concentration can be used to identify damage
 - Less useful for composites => damage often subsurface
- Recent work shows subsurface information can be obtained
 - Carbon fibre composites
 - Non-adiabatic conditions

Motivation & Aims

- Can thermography be used to evaluate subsurface damage in realistic composite components?
- Can fusion of thermal data further extend the capability of thermographic damage inspections?
- Can other full field imaging methods be incorporated to overcome existing limitations?

Test Specimen

- Double tapered C-Spar geometry
 - Industrially relevant case
- 24 plies of AS4 8552
- quasi-isotropic lay up
 - $[(45/0/-45/90)_3]_s$
- Diaphragm formed

End Condition

- Steel plates were manufactured to encapsulate spar ends
- Prevent brooming and local compressive failure
- 20 mm thick plate machined with 15 mm groove
- Two part epoxy adhesive used to bond the spar into the groove
- Hole used to align centroid to loading axis

Experimental Setup

Side Elevation

Plan View

Stereo DIC (white light)
Displacement
Strain

Thermal Imaging
Thermographic NDE
TSA (Cyclic)

Test Plan

- Two test regimes
 - Ramp loading
 - Inspection
- Quasi static loading to increasing maximum loads to progressively induce damage
- Cyclic testing at low loads for TSA and DIC data acquisition

Thermal Results

Prior to Loading

Loading Frequency = 3.1 Hz

Post Loading to 50 kN

Loading Frequency = 3.1 Hz

Digital Image Correlation Strain Results

Future Work : Objectives and Specimens

- **Objective:** develop specimen where damage is more controlled
- Seed delamination
 - Teflon insert in tapered section
 - Initiate delamination
- Repeat test campaign
 - Data fusion before and after loading
 - Comparison to numerical model

Teflon insert

Conclusions

- Thermal methods demonstrated for wrinkle detection
- Building blocks in place for industrially relevant test at structural scale
- Data acquisition and fusion methodology developed
- New specimens being manufactured where damage is more controlled
- Future tests will build upon the existing methods described

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